

Prospective environmental and economic assessment of solar-assisted thermal energy recovery from wastewater through a sequencing batch biofilter granular reactor

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Abstract

The integration of an off-grid solar-assisted heat pump (SHP) and a sequencing batch biofilter granular reactor (SBBGR) for thermal energy recovery from wastewater was assessed by means of a prospective life cycle assessment (LCA) and life cycle costing (LCC), by theoretically scaling up a pilot installation in Bari, Italy, to a full-scale unit designed for 5000 person-equivalents. The LCA and LCC included all activities in the life cycle of the SHP and wastewater treatment plant (WWTP), namely construction, operation and end-of-life. The thermal energy produced by the SHP was assessed as supplying heating and cooling for an air-conditioning system, displacing a conventional air-source heat pump powered by electricity from the grid. This integrated system was compared to a reference situation where wastewater is treated in a conventional WWTP applying activated sludge with no thermal energy recovery system, showing clear environmental benefits in all impact indicators, such as a 42% reduction in greenhouse-gas emissions and a cost reduction of 53%. Several sensitivity analyses confirmed these findings, with the exception of the price rebound effect, which showed that the lower cost of the integrated system could lead to overturning the environmental benefits. As a limitation of the study, the distribution of the supplied air-conditioning to meet a demand off-site the WWTP premises, such as in residential buildings or hotels, was not included. Therefore, our results constitute only a preliminary positive outcome that should be validated in a real-life application.

Keywords: Life cycle assessment (LCA) Life cycle costing (LCC) Wastewater-source heat pump Solar-assisted heat pump Thermal energy recovery

1. Introduction

Wastewater treatment constitutes a substantial energy consumer and source of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. According to Cao (2011), the provision of wastewater treatment services accounts for around 1% of a country's electricity consumption. Also, wastewater is responsible for 4% and 2% of methane and nitrous oxide emissions, respectively (USEPA, 2013). At the same time, urban wastewater constitutes a promising low-grade source of thermal energy, as it is produced steadily, in high volumes and with small temperature variations; it is typically warmer than the environment during winter, but colder in summer, making it suitable for heating and cooling purposes through heat pump systems (CWWA, 2009; Frijns et al., 2013; Meggers and Leibundgut, 2011). Tapping this resource for heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) in buildings is of particular interest, given that buildings account for around 40% of energy consumption (EIA, 2018; Settino et al., 2018) and that energy consumed by HVAC systems is responsible of the largest share of a building's environmental impact (Ochoa et al., 2005; Aliane et al., 2016; Ge et al., 2018).

Centralized systems for thermal energy recovery from wastewater have been in place since the 1980's in Germany, Switzerland and Scandinavia (DWA, 2009), mainly focused on recovery from treated effluents of WWTPs, whereas recovery within sewers or wastewater treatment basins remains elusive, mainly due to biofouling of heat exchangers in contact with untreated wastewater (Chao et al., 2012; Liu et al., 2014). In this context, the novel sequencing batch biofilter granular reactor (SBBGR) constitutes a potential solution to this problem. The SBBGR is an attached-biomass system operating with a complete separation of the biomass from the liquid phase, thus allowing for a reactor zone free of suspended solids where a heat exchanger can be placed (Di Iaconi et al., 2010, 2017; De Sanctis et al., 2017). Due to some additional features of SBBGR biomass (i.e. long sludge age and concentration) it not only prevents biofouling of heat exchangers in the bioreactor, but also favours thermal energy recovery by maximising the conversion of chemical energy stored in water pollution into biochemical heat, as well as by withstanding wastewater temperature changes (Piergrossi et al., 2018).

Coupling of a SBBGR with a solar-assisted heat pump (SHP) has been recently demonstrated at pilot-scale in Bari, Italy (Piergrossi et al., 2018). While the environmental performance of these two technologies have been separately assessed in the past by means of life cycle assessment (LCA) (Di Iaconi et al., 2017; Battles et al., 2010), the resulting benefits or otherwise from their integration remain to be quantified. Furthermore, besides environmental sustainability, economic feasibility is also required for a new technology to find its way into the market and for this reason an evaluation of life cycle costs (LCC) constitutes an equally necessary exercise. In this article we present the results of a prospective LCA and LCC applied to the integration of a SBBGR and SHP for HVAC purposes, as described in Piergrossi et al. (2018), considering its implementation at a larger scale, namely in a hypothetical WWTP designed for 5000 person-equivalents (PE) in a Mediterranean context.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Pilot plant description

The basis for the prospective assessment is a pilot plant installed in Bari, where an existing SBBGR unit was upgraded with a SHP in September 2016 (Fig. 1). Below we provide a brief description of the installation. For detailed descriptions on the SBBGR the reader is referred to Piergrossi et al. (2018).

Fig. 1. The THERBIOR pilot plant.

The SBBGR prototype mainly consists of two columns with a total volume of 300 L. One of such column constitutes the biofilter (3200 mm in height and 220 mm in diameter), which is packed with plastic media where the biomass develops and the biological degradation takes place. The second compartment is known as the aerator (273 mm in diameter and 3200 mm in height). The reactor is operated as a sequencing-fed batch process, consisting of three stages: anaerobic filling, aerobic recirculation between the two columns and eventually a withdrawal phase. The treatment cycle takes 6 h in total, after which the effluent can be discharged without the need for a settling tank. During the recirculation phase, air is provided by means of discontinuous 5-min blowing periods starting every 25 min. In addition, pure oxygen is continuously provided in order to maintain a dissolved oxygen concentration in the aerator within the 15e20 mg/L range. The influent fed to the reactor is real urban wastewater from the local sewer in Bari.

The SHP is a solar-assisted fully off-grid energy system capable of producing, recovering and storing thermal energy. It consists of the main following components:

- A heat pump coupled to a titanium tubular heat exchanger submersed in the SBBGR unit, particularly in the aerator column.
- A reciprocating compressor with 4810 W refrigeration capacity.
- Two short-term thermal latent energy hot and cold storage units filled with phase-change materials (PCM), operating at 53 °C and 0 °C, respectively and with a capacity of 0.3 m³ and 0.5 m³, respectively.
- Energy dissipation devices (condenser and evaporator).
- A rooftop photovoltaic plant with 5.1 kWp capacity and 32 m² module area, powering the entire SHP system.

The SHP is fully off-grid, with the exception of control and HVAC distribution devices, which are supplied from the grid in order to ensure 24-h operation. From a hydraulic point of view, the system is composed of a hot water line and a cold water line. When sufficient solar energy is available, the SHP produces and stores heat in the form of PCM. Conversely, the cold water line produces and stores chilled water in the cold PCM tank. The SHP is used in a low- temperature air-conditioning system supplying a so-called experimental test laboratory (ETL), a room that simulates demand on- site.

2.2. LCA and LCC methods

LCA was carried out with the ISO 14040 and 14044 standards as main methodological guidelines (ISO, 2006a; 2006b), and consequential modelling was used in the inventory analysis, as defined in Weidema (2003, 2009). The software used to model the life cycle was SimaPro version 8.5 (Pre', 2016). Environmental LCC was carried out as described in Hunkeler et al. (2008), that is, accounting for internal costs associated with the life cycle of the product that are covered by any one or more of

the actors in the product life cycle. Both LCA and LCC were aligned in terms of functional unit, system boundaries, etc. As highlighted in the article title, the overall assessment is prospective in the sense that 1) consequential modelling is used in the LCA and 2) the assessment takes a step forward from its actual pilot scale to a commercial scale model. These two methodological aspects allow for a more realistic depiction of a potential deployment of this technology in the market.

2.3. Goal and scenarios assessed

The goal was to assess the expected life-cycle environmental and economic performance of coupling a SHP for thermal energy recovery from urban wastewater with a SBBGR unit, with the aim of providing cooling/heating for residential buildings in a touristic Mediterranean region. We call this the THERBIOR scenario. This is compared to a reference situation for wastewater treatment, in which urban wastewater is treated in a conventional WWTP applying activated sludge (AS) and with no thermal energy recovery system. Fig. 2 shows a conceptual flow diagram for these two scenarios and the respective activities included in the study.

Fig. 2. Flow diagram for the two assessed scenarios: reference (left) and THERBIOR (right). AS: activated sludge; SHP: solar-assisted heat pump

2.4. Geographical scope

The case study considers the implementation of the proposed concept in a hypothetical WWTP located in Bari, where the pilot plant has been installed. This geographical setting is assumed to represent a typical Mediterranean location. The average urban wastewater production in this region is approximately 0.15 m³ per person-equivalent (PE) and day.

2.5. Technological scope: wastewater treatment and sludge disposal

We consider the deployment of this technology in a WWTP designed for treating 5000 PE, or 750 m³/day. The decision to consider a higher scale than the actual experimental one is based on the fact that research scales such as lab- and pilot-scales are not suitable for meaningful environmental (and economic) assessments (Munñoz et al., 2015; Gavankar et al., 2015; Piccinno et al., 2016).

An important aspect linked to the size of the WWTP is the fact that touristic areas are commonly subject to substantial population fluctuations, with peaks in the summer season leading to similar fluctuations in terms of wastewater production. In order to cope with these peaks, WWTPs need to be designed for larger capacities, resulting in suboptimal use of the infrastructure for the most part of the year. In our study we assume that the WWTP is oversized by a factor of 50%. This results in an actual capacity of 3333 PE, which equals 500 m³/day or 182,500 m³/year.

In both scenarios the WWTPs need to discharge a treated effluent complying with the European Directive 91/271/EEC concerning urban wastewater treatment. The AS plant considered as reference includes the following unit operations: mechanical pre-treatment, primary settling, biological treatment with nitrogen removal, secondary settling, sand filtration and disinfection. Excess sludge is subject to aerobic stabilization and dewatering. The SBBGR WWTP involves substantially less unit operations, namely only mechanical pre-treatment and biological treatment in the SBBGR unit

(aerator-biofilter). Excess sludge does not require a stabilization process in this case, but only dewatering. Concerning nutrient (nitrogen and phosphorus) removal, this is in principle not required by current legislation given the size of the assessed WWTPs, however for nitrogen we see in the European Environment Agency's WATERBASE database (EEA, 2016) that 37% of plants in Italy designed for 5000 PE do feature nitrogen removal and for this reason we decided to include it for the reference AS plant. On the other hand, chemical phosphorus removal is less common in these plants, with only 13% of them featuring this operation; for this reason, it is not included in our model. In the case of the SBBGR, both nitrogen and (biological) phosphorus removal are considered, based on previous experimental results with this pilot plant (De Sanctis et al., 2017).

Sludge disposal in the two scenarios is assumed to be through incineration. This is based on an analysis of sludge disposal trends in Europe, using Eurostat data (see SM). This analysis shows that from four main disposal options (use in agriculture, landfilling, incineration and composting), only incineration and composting show a growth trend over time, with this trend being more than three times higher for incineration compared to composting.

2.6. Technological scope: solar-assisted heat pump

Similar size considerations apply to the SHP as those discussed for the WWTPs. The SHP installation at the pilot plant, coupled to a SBBGR treating 269 L wastewater/day, does not properly reflect the expected size and number of components for coupling with a WWTP treating 500 m³/day. In order to overcome this limitation, we carried out a theoretical scale-up of the pilot SHP, by re-dimensioning the individual equipment and/or increasing the number of units. This process was done in detail for the most important components such as photovoltaic plant, tanks, compressor, etc. Also, equipment considered to be part of the pilot plant only for research purposes was discarded in the full-scale design. The resulting SHP model had a capacity of 244 kW heating and 160 kW cooling, powered by 1225 m² of photovoltaic modules.

2.7. Technological scope: substituted grid power-driven heat pump

The heating and cooling service fulfilled by the implementation of the proposed concept is assumed to substitute heating and cooling supplied by an air-source heat pump driven by electricity from the grid, having the same heating and cooling capacity as the SHP. This is in accordance with a similar study (Batlles et al., 2010) evaluating a solar HVAC system in Almería, Spain, with very similar climatic conditions to Bari. The choice of a single heat pump over e.g. a combined heat pump (for cooling) and a boiler (for heating) can be justified based on the fact that given the relatively mild winters in the Mediterranean region, the installation of two different systems is not justified, as the heat pump can deliver both functions. A survey in Spain (IDAE, 2016) shows that in the Mediterranean regions of the country heat pumps are more commonly used for residential and commercial uses compared to the Northern Atlantic regions, with colder climate, where lower cooling and higher heating requirements are found. As for the type of heat pump, this same survey in Spain shows that air-source heat pumps dominate both in terms of installed units (78% of total) and installed capacity (71% of total) over water-source and geothermal heat pumps.

2.8. Functional unit

The function of the system under study is established as providing treatment for urban wastewater. The THERBIOR scenario, however, provides an additional function, namely the recovery of thermal energy to be used for cooling/heating. This additional function is dealt with in the LCA and LCC by means of substitution. The functional unit and reference flow used in the study is the treatment of 1 m³ of urban wastewater with the following composition, obtained from the WWTP at Putignano (Southern Italy): 937 mg chemical oxygen demand (COD)/L, 93 mg total nitrogen (TN)/L, 625 mg

suspended solids (SS)/L and 10 mg total phosphorus (TP)/L.

2.9. Limitations

We can highlight two main limitations in our assessment, one related to energy use and the other related to wastewater treatment. From the energy point of view, the purpose of our research project was to assess the potential for thermal energy recovery from wastewater through the innovative SHP. In the pilot plant the recovered energy is used to provide heating and cooling to the simulated ETL attached to the plant. In a full-scale deployment of this technology, however, the heating and cooling demand could be located outside of the WWTP premises, in hotels, residences or office buildings. In our study we do not include the transport of the produced energy to a hypothetical building off-site. We instead quantify the service as if it was supplied on-site (no distribution network, no losses).

From the wastewater treatment side, a relevant aspect that could be addressed is the fate and potential toxicity impacts of heavy metals and organic micropollutants present in the raw wastewater and how these differ when a SBBGR is used instead of activated sludge. Unfortunately, in this study we lacked information on the corresponding performance of SBBGR vs. activated sludge with regard to these pollutants. The concentration of some heavy metals and organic micropollutants in SBBGR influent and effluent was measured during a previous study on wastewater reuse in agriculture (De Sanctis et al., 2017). Most of the selected micro- pollutants were not detected in the wastewater used in that study. In the inventory analysis we do not quantify emissions to air, water or soil from these pollutants in wastewater.

2.10. Impact assessment method

The method used for impact assessment in the LCA study is Stepwise 2006, version 1.5. The method is described and documented in Annex II in Weidema et al. (2007) and in Weidema (2009). Stepwise is capable of providing results at the level of midpoints (characterization) and endpoints (damage). At the endpoint level, each impact category is expressed in monetary units (Euro), measuring environmental damage. In total, Step- wise2006 includes a total of 16 impact categories commonly used in LCA, however, given the lack of data at the inventory level on the presence and fate of micropollutants in wastewater, we decided to exclude freshwater ecotoxicity from the set of environmental impact categories assessed.

2.11. Data collection for life cycle assessment

The life cycle model was built using the consequential library available in ecoinvent v.3.2 (Ecoinvent, 2018) as background data- base, whereas a variety of primary data sources were used in the inventory analysis. In this section we outline the main sources and assumptions, whereas a summarised mass and energy balance is provided in Fig. 3 for the two scenarios (excluding sludge disposal, capital equipment and the background system). For complete and detailed inventory tables the reader is referred to the SM.

Fig. 3. Summarised mass and energy balance for the two assessed scenarios during the operation life cycle phase: reference (left) and THERBIOR (right). * 0.14 kWh is the electricity consumption of SHP and all peripheral components such as circulation pumps and fan-coil unit.

Construction of a conventional WWTP designed for treating 750 m³/day was estimated with a linear regression using existing inventories for WWTPs of different capacities in Switzerland, available in the ecoinvent database. These same data were the basis for the SBBGR WWTP construction, for which no data were found. We took the assumption that infrastructure material inputs are proportional to investment costs, meaning that the lower investment cost of a SBBGR WWTP (see 2.12) leads to a proportional infrastructure material reduction. WWTP operation included inputs of electricity, sodium hypochlorite for disinfection, polyelectrolyte for sludge dewatering, sodium hydroxide for sand filter cleaning and sand replacements for this filter. All material inputs were quantified based on literature (see SM) with the exception of electricity consumption, which was taken from the WWTP at Putignano. This plant has recently been partially upgraded to a SBBGR treatment, allowing us to get accurate data for both conventional (activated sludge) and SBBGR treatment. A detailed theoretical mass balance was established for the WWTPs, based on the influent and effluent composition, using WW LCI, a life cycle inventory model for chemicals discharged in wastewater (Muñoz et al., 2016; Kalbar et al., 2017). With this model we estimated direct emissions from the WWTP to air (CO₂, N₂O), to water (NO₃, NH₄, TP) as well as sludge production, which resulted in 0.51 kg dry mass/m³ for the conventional WWTP after aerobic digestion and 0.14 kg dry mass/m³ for the SBBGR WWTP. WW LCI was also used to model two additional processes. Firstly, emissions of CO₂ and N₂O resulting from the ultimate degradation in the aquatic environment of organics and nutrients in the treated effluent. Secondly, to model sludge disposal by incineration, which involves transport of dewatered sludge, drying to a content of 90% dry mass and combustion with energy recovery (see SM for details).

The inventory for construction of the SHP, based on a theoretical scale-up of the pilot, was accomplished by first compiling a detailed bill of materials for this pilot, which resulted in 1.7 tonnes of equipment. In the scale-up we enlarged, changed and adapted all this equipment, resulting in a SHP embedding 56 tonnes of equipment, including a 190 kWp photovoltaic plant with 1225 m² module area. In order to annualize the consumption of equipment, service lives in years were defined for each type of component, ranging from 7 years for electronics to 30 years for structural elements. One of the difficulties faced to build this inventory lies in the current lack of data sets in ecoinvent to represent some of the machinery and equipment installed in the SHP. In the SM we report in detail how we adapted and linked our data to the ecoinvent database.

The operation of the SHP includes some grid electricity needed to keep the heating/cooling distribution running during the night, but more importantly, the amount of heating/cooling produced and recovered by this system, expressed in MJ. This consists of two contributions: the solar-powered heat pump itself and the thermal energy recovery from wastewater. The first contribution is quantified

considering the SHP heating and cooling capacity, of 244 kW and 160 kW, respectively and an end-user heating and cooling demand of 632 h/year and 864 h/year, respectively for a Mediterranean location (Batlles et al., 2010). Concerning thermal energy recovery from wastewater, as described in Piergrossi et al. (2018), it was found that a substantial share of the recovered thermal energy was sensible heat from solar radiation, i.e. heating of the SBBGR columns by direct exposure to sunlight, as they are placed above ground (see Fig. 1). However, in a full-scale SBBGR unit the tanks would be instead placed on the ground (similarly to conventional activated sludge tanks), and therefore the heating contribution from sunlight would not occur. A detailed energy balance of the SBBGR reactor revealed that in average, approximately 50% of the recovered energy is due to solar exposure of the reactor (Portillo, 2017). In our scale-up calculations we excluded this contribution and quantified the recoverable thermal energy as 13.8 MJ per m³ wastewater, and the actually recovered energy as 4.6 MJ/m³, given that the SHP can only operate during daylight (8 h/day). Considering the two contributions (SHP and wastewater), the total thermal energy recovered is 10.4 MJ/m³.

The inventory for the substituted air-source heat pump was quantified based on a mirror design of the up-scaled SHP where the photovoltaic system was removed and power from the grid was instead considered.

Finally, electricity production in Italy, which supplies all the above activities, was modelled considering only flexible suppliers in the period 2012e2020, resulting in a grid mix containing 88% renewably-sourced electricity (see SM for details).

2.12. Data collection for life cycle costing

Costs assessed included investment and operation, whereas decommissioning costs were neglected (Muñoz, 2006). Investment costs were annualized using the so-called capital recovery factor (CRF), as a function of service life in years and interest rate. The latter was taken as 1%, which corresponds to the GDP-weighted Euro area ten-year sovereign bond yield, according to the European Central Bank at the beginning of 2018 (ECB, 2018). As in the previous section, below we only provide a summary of the main data sources and assumptions, whereas detailed cost calculations are available in the SM.

Investment costs for a conventional and SBBGR WWTP were established as 350V and 224V per PE, respectively, based on information supplied by the integrated water services operator in the Apulia region, which operates the Putignano WWTP upgraded to SBBGR. Investment cost for the up-scaled SHP was estimated close to 906,000 V, based on the total equipment cost plus installation, engineering costs, etc. The CRF for these investments was calculated assuming a service life of 30 years for the WWTP and 20 years for the SHP.

Operation costs for the WWTP included electricity costs, other operation costs and sludge disposal. Electricity costs for Italian industrial consumers was obtained from EUROSTAT (2018) as 0.185 V/kWh. Other operation costs were estimated as 3% of the investment cost, annually (COWI, 2010), and sludge disposal costs included transport and incineration costs, estimated for Italy as 203 V per tonne in wet weight, based on Diaz et al. (2015) and UN-Habitat (2008). Operation costs for the SHP included grid electricity consumption for equipment running 24 h and maintenance costs. The latter were estimated as 3% of the investment costs, annually. This is the average value obtained from a study on life cycle costs of HVAC systems (Wu and Clements-Croome, 2007).

The substituted air-source heat pump costs were quantified following a similar approach as in the SHP. Investment costs were estimated as 167,600V with a service life of 15 years. Operation costs included electricity and maintenance, taking the same approach as in the SHP. In this case, the grid electricity consumption is 0.144 kWh per MJ heating/cooling. Overall, the unitary cost of this pump results in 0.043V per MJ heating/cooling.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Life cycle impact assessment

Table 1 shows the life cycle impact assessment results for the two scenarios, at both midpoint and endpoint level. While at midpoint each indicator has its own specific units, at endpoint level they are all expressed in monetary units. At midpoint level we can see that the THERBIOR scenario shows lower environmental impact in all 15 indicators, with a reduction in impact ranging from 19% in mineral extraction to 93% in ozone layer depletion. In nature occupation, the THERBIOR scenario presents a negative score, meaning a net beneficial effect on this indicator. The inclusion of results at endpoint level is useful to identify those impact indicators where the system has the highest contribution to environmental damages. It can be seen in Table 1 that in our case study this corresponds to global warming, respiratory inorganics and freshwater eutrophication, with the first one of these three having the highest magnitude.

Table 1. Life cycle impact assessment results at midpoint and endpoint level per m³ wastewater.

Impact category	Midpoint		Endpoint			
	Unit	Reference	THERBIOR	Unit	Reference	THERBIOR
Human toxicity, carcinogens	kg C ₂ H ₃ Cl-eq into air	0.023	0.011	√	0.006	0.003
Human toxicity, non-carcinogens	kg C ₂ H ₃ Cl-eq into air	0.042	0.015	√	0.011	0.004
Respiratory inorganics	kg PM _{2.5} -eq	0.00086	0.00035	√	0.058	0.024
Ionizing radiation	Bq Carbon-14 into air	0.60	-0.19	√	1.2E-05	-3.8E-06
Ozone layer depletion	kg CFC11-eq	7.5E-08	5.0E-09	√	7.7E-06	5.2E-07
Ecotoxicity, terrestrial	kg triethylene glycol-eq into soil	5.5	3.1	√	1.2E-04	1.7E-04
Nature occupation	m ² agr. land	0.037	-0.001	√	0.0045	-0.0001
Global warming	kg CO ₂ -eq	0.82	0.47	√	0.068	0.039
Acidification	m ² unprotected ecosystem	0.044	0.015	√	0.0003	0.0001
Eutrophication, aquatic	kg NO ₃ -eq	0.33	0.21	√	0.033	0.021
Eutrophication, terrestrial	m ² unprotected ecosystem	0.11	0.03	√	0.0014	0.0004
Respiratory organics	Person\$ppm\$h	0.00059	0.00023	√	1.5E-04	6.0E-05
Photochemical ozone, vegetation	m ² \$ppm\$hour	6.8	2.4	√	0.0025	0.0009
Non-renewable energy	Megajoule	8.9	2.5	√	0	0
Mineral extraction	Megajoule	0.12	0.10	√	5.0E-04	4.0E-04

Fig. 4 shows a contribution analysis of the global warming indicator, expressing GHG emissions in CO₂-eq. It must be stressed that biogenic CO₂ emissions from the degradation of organic matter in wastewater are considered to be climate-neutral in our analysis. The graph shows that GHG emissions are especially lower for the THERBIOR scenario in two aspects: sludge disposal and heat pump substitution. With regard to sludge disposal, there is a clear advantage for the SBBGR due to its substantially lower sludge production. This means less transport, less fuel requirements to dry sludge prior to incineration, and less incineration emissions. Overall, GHG emissions related to sludge disposal are reduced by a factor four. Concerning heat pump substitution, this is shown with a negative sign in the graph, meaning that 0.27 kg CO₂-eq are avoided per m³ wastewater. These emissions are related to the (avoided) production, operation and end of life of a conventional heat pump powered by the grid. There is no such saving in the reference scenario, as there is no thermal energy production in that case. Overall, in the THERBIOR scenario the SHP leads to a total emission over the life cycle (construction, operation, end of life) of 0.16 kg CO₂-eq/m³, but this is more than compensated by the aforementioned saving of 0.27 kg CO₂-eq/m³. It is also worth mentioning that the THERBIOR scenario also involves a GHG reduction during WWTP construction, however this result is subject to uncertainty, as we have assumed that infrastructure impacts are directly linked to investment costs. It seems reasonable though that the much simpler layout of a SBBGR WWTP should involve, to some extent, a lower need for construction materials such as concrete and reinforced steel, among others.

Fig. 4. Contribution analysis for global warming in kg CO₂-eq/m³.

An equivalent contribution analysis for respiratory inorganics (see SM) reveals approximately the same patterns we see in Fig. 4. For freshwater eutrophication, though, the contribution analysis (see SM) shows that life cycle impacts are completely dominated by the release of nutrients in the effluent (TN and TP). Freshwater eutrophication puts a special focus on phosphorus, which is removed at higher rates by the SBBGR WWTP, thanks to biological phosphorus removal. This environmental benefit for the THERBIOR scenario can be considered valid only for cases where WWTPs discharge in continental waters, where eutrophication is typically limited by phosphorus availability. In a situation in which the WWTPs discharge to the sea, where eutrophication is limited by nitrogen availability, the results for both scenarios would be similar.

3.2. Life cycle costs

In Table 2 we see that the THERBIOR scenario involves a substantial cost reduction, of -0.74 V/m³ or 135,800 V/year. Considering the WWTP design capacity, of 5000 PE, our results suggest a potential saving of 27 V/PE/year. This scenario involves higher costs in terms of SHP investment, operation and maintenance. These costs add up to 0.45 V/m³, whereas the benefit, that is, the avoided cost of a conventional air-source heat pump, is -0.45 V/m³. In summary, from a financial point of view, the installation of the SHP system reaches the break-even point, but fails to provide a net economic benefit. Hence, the overall reduction in life cycle costs we observe in the THERBIOR scenario is entirely attributed to the introduction of the SBBGR.

Table 2. Life cycle costs in V/m³.

Activity	Reference	THERBIOR	Difference ^a
WWTP Investment	0.37	0.24	-0.13
WWTP operation excluding electricity	0.29	0.18	-0.10
WWTP electricity	0.23	0.14	-0.09
Sludge transport	0.06	0.01	-0.05
Sludge disposal	0.46	0.09	-0.37
SHP investment	0	0.28	0.28
SHP electricity	0	0.03	0.03
SHP maintenance	0	0.15	0.15
Substituted heat pump	0	-0.45	-0.45
Total	1.41	0.67	-0.74

^a Calculated as THERBIOR minus reference.

3.3. Sensitivity and scenario analyses

We have performed a set of sensitivity and scenario analyses to check the robustness of our results both at the environmental and economic level. With regard to the environmental assessment, we present four analyses, for which further information is available in the SM:

- Sludge disposal by means of composting followed by use in agriculture, instead of incineration. This is modelled with WW LCI (Kalbar et al., 2017).
- Electricity production from coal instead of the prospective Italian grid mix mainly composed by renewables.
- Inclusion of indirect land use change (iLUC) effects associated to a higher need for land in the THERBIOR scenario. This is modelled with the method developed by Schmidt et al. (2015), assumed displaced land is used for agriculture.
- Inclusion of the rebound effect due to cost difference between the two scenarios (Consequential-LCA, 2015). This effect is modelled for Italy with the database Exiobase (Wood et al. 2015).
- Addition of a battery bank allowing the SHP to recover thermal energy from wastewater during night hours.

In order to facilitate the interpretation of results, we focus on the influence of the above considerations in the global warming indicator. The results are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Results of several sensitivity analyses for global warming in kg CO₂-eq/m³.

Analysis	Reference	THERBIOR
Baseline	0.82	0.47
Sludge composting	1.11	0.50
Electricity from coal	1.43	-0.24
iLUC	0.82	0.48
Rebound effect	0.82	0.86
Battery bank ^a	0.82	0.31

^a Applies to the THERBIOR scenario only.

Table 3 shows that most analyses reinforce the preference for the THERBIOR scenario. Sludge composting tends to increase GHG emissions compared to incineration, but this does not affect the better ranking of THERBIOR. Considering coal as the marginal electricity supply can be considered as a worst case, that in fact leads to a bigger gap between THERBIOR and the reference, due to a higher environmental benefit associated to substituting a grid power-driven heat pump. However, this analysis is only representative for countries where substantial increase in the use of fossil fuels for electricity production is expected, which is in principle not the case in the EU. Concerning iLUC, the systems under study seem to have little sensitivity to this aspect, even though the SBBGR WWTP is expected to require more land to accommodate the photovoltaic plant. The introduction of a lead-acid battery bank also appears to be favourable to the THERBIOR scenario, as it allows the SHP to recover energy from wastewater continuously rather than just 8 h per day, substantially increasing the benefit from substituting a conventional heat pump. Last but not least, we see that the rebound effect due to the cost difference between the two scenarios makes the THERBIOR GHG emissions jump above those of the reference. Exiobase data show that in Italy, each V spent leads in average to 0.52 kg CO₂-eq. This means that THERBIOR, by freeing 0.74 V/m³ has a potential rebound effect of 0.39 kg CO₂-eq/m³. This effect completely offsets the GHG reduction obtained in our base-line assessment. This analysis is subject to uncertainty since it is the result of using data from two completely different databases (ecoinvent for the product system and Exiobase for the rebound effect) but constitutes an interesting finding from a sustainability point of view, which to our knowledge is typically omitted in LCA studies.

As for LCC, in Table 4 we show the result of a sensitivity analysis on key model input variables, where we re-calculate cost when each variable change by $\pm 25\%$, one at a time. We performed this analysis for 21 variables in total, although in Table 4 we only show the results for the top 10 most sensitive variables.

Table 4. Results of several sensitivity analyses on life cycle costs, indicating the difference in costs between the reference and

THERBIOR scenarios (V/m³). A negative result implies the THERBIOR scenario leads to a cost saving compared to the reference.

Variable	Default value for variable	THERBIOR minus reference if variable increases by 25%	THERBIOR minus reference if variable decreases by 25%
Investment SHP (V)	905,829	−0.64	−0.83
Sludge production (kg dm/m ³)	0.14 (THERBIOR) 0.51 (reference)	−0.85	−0.66
Sludge disposal cost (V/kg ww)	0.18	−0.84	−0.67
Electricity cost (V/kWh)	0.185	−0.83	−0.73
Dry mass content in sludge (%)	28% (THERBIOR) 20% (reference)	−0.66	−0.85
SHP service life (yr)	20	−0.79	−0.68
Potential thermal recovery from wastewater (MJ/m ³ /d)	13.8	−0.79	−0.71
Usage conventional heat pump/SHP (hours/year)	1496	−0.70	−0.80
Investment conventional heat pump (V)	167,603	−0.79	−0.71
SHP maintenance costs (% of investment/year)	3%	−0.71	−0.77

The sensitivity analysis in Table 4 shows negative figures in all cases, i.e. for all variables a change of $\pm 25\%$ does not lead to a preference for the reference scenario. Our baseline saving is -0.74 V/m³ and in Table 4 we see this saving ranges from -0.64 to -0.85 V/m³ depending on which variable is affected. The most sensitive variables in the model appear to be the amount of sludge produced and the investment cost of the SHP.

Besides the above sensitivity analyses on costs, we also subjected two of the cases in Table 3 to a parallel calculation of life cycle costs, in particular the installation of a battery bank and the alternative disposal of sludge through composting. On the one hand, our results show that if composting is considered, the cost of both the reference and THERBIOR scenarios decrease to 1.18 V/m³ and 0.62 V/m³, respectively. In this situation the net saving by THERBIOR substantially decreases from -0.74 V/m³ to -0.56 V/m³. On the other hand, the installation of the battery bank in the THERBIOR scenario incurs in a slight increase in costs, from 0.67 V/m³ to 0.70 V/m³, due to the investment cost of the batteries. Hence, the battery bank represents an environmental improvement, but an additional net cost.

4. Discussion

Our LCA results concerning wastewater treatment can be compared to those of Di Iaconi et al. (2017), who compared a conventional AS WWTP with upgrading the latter to a SBBGR WWTP. In terms of GHG emissions, they found a higher impact for the SBBGR, due to increased 1) N₂O emissions from denitrification, which their AS WWTP did not perform and 2) electricity for recirculation between the biofilter and aerator. In our study both the AS WWTP and SBBGR have nitrogen removal, whereby N₂O emissions are in the same order of magnitude. Concerning electricity, Di Iaconi et al. (2017) used energy consumption data at the pilot-scale, whereas in our study real data from the SBBGR upgrade at the Putignano WWTP were used, actually showing lower electricity consumption compared to the AS process in this same plant (see SM). In terms of freshwater eutrophication, Di Iaconi et al. (2017) also show higher impact for the SBBGR, due to higher TP emissions observed in the pilot-scale reactor. However, more recent research with this same unit has shown high TP removal rates of up to 62% (De Sanctis et al., 2017). On eutrophication, it could be argued that the scale chosen (5000 PE) benefits the SBBGR, given that at this scale P removal is not compulsory in the EU. In this way, the reference scenario discharges more P to the aquatic environment. In a situation where P removal becomes compulsory, such as in population agglomerations >10,000 PE, our results most likely would not show a benefit for the SBBGR in the eutrophication indicator, since the reference scenario would also apply P removal, by means of e.g. chemical coagulants. However, this would come at the expense of an increased impact for the reference scenario in other indicators, such as GHG emissions, due to the

additional production of the required coagulants.

As reported in section 2.9, the fate and potential toxicity impacts of heavy metals and organic micropollutants present in the SBBGR and activated sludge effluents have not been investigated during this experimental campaign. Thus, the authors decided not to consider these elements in the LCA. However, the effect of SBBGR treatment on heavy metals and some organic micropollutants was investigated in a previous study by De Sanctis et al. (2017) while treating wastewater coming from small villages. In the cited study, the SBBGR showed removal efficiencies of heavy metals similar to those reported by Feng et al. (2018) in a study on twelve conventional full-scale WWTPs. As for organic micropollutants, most of them were absent in both wastewater and SBBGR influent. With regard to the LCA results in terms of energy recovery, we can say our results agree with those of Batlles et al. (2010), in the sense that the introduction of a solar-assisted heat pump for HVAC systems involves a reduction in environmental impact compared to a grid power-driven heat pump. As discussed in the previous paragraph, it could be again argued that the scale chosen (5000 PE) provides an advantage to the THERBIOR scenario, since bigger AS WWTPs can implement energy recovery through anaerobic digestion of sludge. Anaerobic digestion is not an option to the SBBGR technology regardless of plant size (given its relatively low sludge production and low volatile solids content in sludge), however we argue that anaerobic digestion would only present an overall environmental advantage to the reference scenario as long as the digested sludge is not disposed by means of incineration. This is due to the fact that energy recovered through anaerobic digestion would be offset by the additional energy demand of the incineration plant, as digested sludge would have a lower calorific value. This consideration is supported by the literature reporting that calorific value of sludge can be lowered from about 40 to 60% by anaerobic digestion process (Gezer Gorcec et al., 2016). Thus, in a context where incineration is the long-term marginal disposal option, our results are likely to remain valid regardless of the presence or absence of anaerobic digestion.

In terms of life cycle costs, we can compare our results with those of Di Iaconi et al. (2017), who found a potential saving of up to 11 V/PE/year when converting a AS WWTP into a SBBGR WWTP (without SHP). The reasons for our higher saving are manifold: Di Iaconi et al. (2017) assessed the conversion of an existing AS plant to a SBBGR rather than an ex-novo construction. In their study, the SBBGR involves an investment cost, whereas the investment is zero for the existing plant. In our study we capture the investment costs for both types of plants, showing that the SBBGR involves an investment saving. In addition, we find lower costs in areas such as power consumption and other operation costs, which the study by Di Iaconi et al. (2017) did not reveal, as it used data at pilot-scale and because it used more conservative assumptions. Both studies do agree, though, in identifying sludge disposal as the aspect in which costs are reduced to the largest extent.

Concerning uncertainty in our assessment as a whole, we lacked a systematic probabilistic uncertainty analysis of the e.g. Monte- Carlo type, although our battery of sensitivity and alternative scenario analyses seemed to point to the robustness of our results. Probably the main source of uncertainty in this kind of assessment lies in trying to predict what this technology will look like when implemented at large scale. The fact that we made a theoretical scale-up of the plant could be seen as a source of uncertainty. We could have used the original pilot plant data, for which we had precise measured data, but as other authors have argued (Muñoz et al., 2015; Gavankar et al., 2015; Piccinno et al., 2016), this higher precision comes at the cost of overall higher uncertainty, since it leads to describing the technology in unrealistic conditions, an example of this in our study being the potential overestimation of energy recovery due to exposure of the pilot plant to sunlight, as described in section 2.11. For this reason, we think that at the end of the day our theoretical scale-up approach does reduce rather than increase uncertainty.

The implementation of this technology could target both new WWTPs as well as existing WWTPs upgraded from a conventional treatment to SBBGR, as described in Di Iaconi et al. (2017). From the point of view of the recovered energy (cooling/heating) end user, medium- and large-sized buildings

should be targeted in Medi- terranean areas, where the number of days with more than 6 h of sunlight is significant. Hotels, hospitals and residence halls (students and elderly) are examples of such end users.

5. Conclusions

Coupling of a sequencing batch biofilter granular reactor (SBBGR) with an off-grid solar-assisted heat pump (SHP) has been shown to provide an environmental and economic benefit from a life cycle perspective, when these two technologies are integrated to obtain renewably-sourced heating and cooling for buildings (so- called THERBIOR scenario), compared to a conventional wastewater treatment plant (reference scenario).

The environmental assessment through LCA, considering 15 commonly used impact indicators, shows preference for the THERBIOR scenario in all indicators, showing, as an example, a 42% reduction in greenhouse-gas emissions. A contribution analysis shows that this reduction is mainly due to lower sludge disposal requirements by the SBBGR as well as by the substitution of a conventional grid-powered heat pump thanks to the introduction of the SHP.

In parallel, life cycle costs are reduced by 53% compared to the reference scenario, representing a saving of 27V per person- equivalent/year or above 135,000 V per year for the chosen plant size. The contribution analysis of life cycle costs shows that this cost reduction is mainly due to the lower investment and operation costs of the SBBGR, rather than to the introduction of the SHP.

Several sensitivity analyses and alternative scenario analyses reinforce the above conclusions in terms of both environmental impacts and costs. As an exception to the latter, it was found that the price rebound effect due to the lower cost of the THERBIOR scenario could completely offset its environmental benefits, considering the spending of these economic resources in average production and consumption in Italy. Although the results of this particular sensitivity analysis are uncertain, our case study shows how relevant rebound effects are in the context of environmental assessment of new technologies.

Also, we should point two main limitations in this study. We did not address the potential benefits (or otherwise) of using SBBGR vs. activated sludge in terms of eco-toxicity impacts, as we lacked data on the relative performance of these two systems on degradation and/or removal of micro-pollutants such as heavy metals, pharmaceuticals and personal-care products. Finally, we assessed the provision of air conditioning as if the demand was on-site, however, most of this demand is expected to be located off-site in e.g. residential buildings or hotels. The environmental impact and cost (including potential energy losses) of distributing this air conditioning to neighbouring buildings has not been included in our assessment. Therefore, our results constitute only a preliminary positive outcome that should be validated in a real-life application.

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